

COMMON FRAMEWORK FOR THE INDIVIDUAL INTERVIEWS AND FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSIONS

DELIAH

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1 INTRODUCTION

Democratic Literacy and Humour (DELIAH) examines the multifaceted role of humour in artistic forms, cultural spaces, and online and offline fora, identifying how humour can either support or undermine democratic participation and processes in Europe. Work Package 6 investigates how certain practices and strategies of humour are deployed in times of conflict during the full-scale Russo-Ukrainian War (2022-) and the rise of a new, populist government in Slovakia following the September 2023 elections. Deliverable 6.1 will be used for Task 6.1, which focuses on humour practices of Ukrainian displaced people in Belgium and Estonia. Each of two country cases was analysed via online observation, and now ethnography continues by means of open-ended interviews and focus groups. This framework is informed by findings from the previous research on online humour. The total sample groups for the interviews and focus groups involve approximately 50 participants per country, with roughly half of them participating in individual interviews and the other half in focus groups. The overall aim is to understand the experiences of adjustment among displaced Ukrainians (e.g., Ukrainian refugees, Ukrainian forced migrants) as they crystallise in various forms and practices of humour as well as the reasons for their success. Approximately four focus groups will be conducted in Estonia and Belgium, with each group consisting of four to six participants.

This document presents the common framework intended to guide the in-depth individual interviews and focus groups. This document discusses the objectives of these research methods, the composition of the groups, and the socio-demographic variables to be recorded for participants, and the individual interview and focus group scripts.

2 OBJECTIVES OF THE INDIVIDUAL INTERVIEWS AND FOCUS GROUPS

In-depth individual interviews are one of the most common methods of data collection in qualitative research.¹ It is commonly understood as a one-on-one conversation with a purpose, specifically, between an interviewer (researcher) and an interviewee (participant) in which the latter is invited to share and discuss their personal experiences related to a topic of interest to the research. This relation can be seen as fundamentally collaborative, as the participant's narrative is co-constructed through interaction with the interviewer, guided by a flexible interview protocol that encourages open-ended narration and reflection on specific topics. Therefore, one of the purposes of individual interviews is to capture contextualized accounts of the interlocutor's lived experience.²

In-depth interviews are considered a more 'private' method than focus groups. This makes them particularly suitable for eliciting personal and sensitive materials, such as accounts of displacement and war, as well as investigating individual's self-conceptions, interpretations, and behaviours. Despite the

¹ Pertti Alasuutari et al., eds., *The SAGE Handbook of Social Research Methods* (SAGE, 2008), 266.

² Ruthellen Josselson, *Interviewing for Qualitative Inquiry: A Relational Approach.*, *Interviewing for Qualitative Inquiry: A Relational Approach.* (The Guilford Press, 2013), 5.

strengths of this research method, in-depth individual interviews do not allow to observe social interactions and the collective negotiation of meaning. Furthermore, we must recognise that interviews are shaped by intersubjective context, including power relations and the researcher's positionality.³

Individual interviews can be combined with **focus group interviews** to explore the phenomenon under study in a more complementary manner. Typically homogenous in composition, focus groups are defined as moderator-led informal discussions among selected participants (commonly four to twelve individuals) focused on a particular topic.⁴ Focus group methodology can be adopted to observe social interactions and elicit collective ideas and shared experience. Smaller groups – from four to eight people – are more conducive to balanced interaction, creating a more inclusive environment in which each participant is likely to contribute to the discussion. Such settings allow to generate richer and more nuanced data. Moreover, focus groups enable to obtain unique materials and insights that would be less accessible without the interaction found in a group, i.e. to capture dynamics of everyday practices.⁵

In the context of the DELIAH project, individual in-depth interviews will be employed to investigate displaced Ukrainians' personal experiences with war, displacement, and adjustment in host societies through the lens of humour practices. At the same time, focus groups will be used to explore humour as a collective and socially negotiated phenomena among Ukrainian refugees, allowing us to observe how shared ideas emerge and are disseminated and received by other group members. Both methods aim to enhance an emic understanding of humour, its variety of forms, and dynamics of everyday practices. The multi-method approach is intended to provide data completeness as each method captures different aspects of the role of humour in the adjustment process of displaced Ukrainians.

Specifically, the objectives of this study conducted via these research methods are:

- *Identify common themes and topics in narratives shared by Ukrainian refugees about their experience of displacement, including their adjustment to host societies and their perceptions of broader social and political attitudes;*
- *More specifically, examine the functions of humour as it emerges in individual interviews and focus groups among Ukrainian refugees, primarily from an emic perspective, while considering their possible alignment with existing frameworks such as the Humour Styles taxonomy (affiliative, aggressive, self-enhancing, self-defeating);*
- *Analyse forms of humour from an emic perspective, with particular attention to conversational humour in focus groups, an under-researched area. This includes lexemes, phrasemes, witticisms, retorts, teasing, banter, putdowns, self-denigrating humour, and anecdotes;⁶*
- *Explore whether there is a relationship between gender and humour, including both its forms and functions;*
- *Identify forms of humour from an emic perspective, focusing especially on conversational humour in focus groups, an area that remains under-researched. This includes lexemes, phrasemes, witticisms, retorts, teasing, banter, putdowns, self-denigrating humour and anecdotes.*

³ Ibid, 9

⁴ L. C. Beck et al., "Using Focus Group Sessions before Decisions Are Made," *North Carolina Medical Journal* 47, no. 2 (1986): 73–74.

⁵ David Morgan, *Focus Groups as Qualitative Research* (SAGE Publications, Inc., 1997), 12, <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412984287>.

⁶ Marta Dynel, "Beyond a Joke: Types of Conversational Humour," *Language and Linguistics Compass* 3, no. 5 (2009): 1296, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-818X.2009.00152.x>.

The materials of this ethnographic research will be transcribed, analysed, and summarised in a co-authored report about refugees' humour in times of conflict, in particular Ukrainian displaced citizens in Belgium and Estonia. The findings will contribute to the formulation of further research into the relationship between humour and refugees.

3 RECRUITMENT METHOD

The interlocutors for the open-ended interviews and focus groups will be recruited through the advertisement posted in thematic Ukrainian groups on social media platforms such as Facebook and Telegram in the selected countries (e.g. 'Ukrainians in Estonia/Belgium (Українці в Естонії/Бельгії)', 'Ukraina sõbrad Eestis (Friends of Ukraine in Estonia)' and so forth). Previous research indicated that these platforms are among the most used by Ukrainian refugees.⁷ Additionally, snowball sampling will be employed and is expected to play a crucial role in engaging participants in the study. This approach entails the active involvement of participants in identifying potential respondents for the research study, i.e. interlocuter's friends or family members who meet the criteria. It will allow to organise the research around pre-existing groups, which is advantageous for the exploration of collective experience and identity in the context of the Ukrainian refugees.

Interviews will take place either in person or online (via Telegram, WhatsApp, Messenger, or mobile phone call), depending on what the interviewee finds most convenient. It is preferable to conduct focus groups in an offline setting.

Participants will have the option of taking part in either the individual interview or focus group. Only one interview is planned per respondent, however, a follow-up meeting may be requested to clarify important points if necessary. Prior to an interview or focus group, each participant will be provided with a consent form and tentative questionnaire in order to know what to expect.

Each interlocutor will be compensated for their time with a €35 voucher for a local grocery store (Lidl, Rimi, or Maxima in Estonia; Aldi, Delhaize, or Carrefour in Belgium)

4 DETAILED DESCRIPTION OF PARTICIPANTS INVESTIGATED AND COMPOSITION OF THE FOCUS GROUPS

In-depth ethnographic interviews and focus groups will be conducted with consent individuals. Potential participants should meet the following criteria: they must be adult (of the legal age of majority) Ukrainian nationals displaced from Ukraine since February 2022 because of the war and residing in Belgium or Estonia. The age of majority of participants in both countries is 18 years, meaning that they can provide informed consent and consent for processing personal data without the need for parental or guardian approval.⁸ Therefore, the participants must be at least 18 years old and be holders of a refugee status, such

⁷ UNHCR. 2022. "Profiles, Needs & Intentions of Refugees From Ukraine." <https://data.unhcr.org/en/dataviz/246>.

⁸ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights [EUFRA]. "Age of Majority," n.d. <https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2017/mapping-minimum-age-requirements/age-majority>.

as temporary or international protection (in the case of Estonia). In Estonia, Ukrainians may have obtained a temporary residence permit granted on the basis of temporary protection (i.e. a residence permit); such cases still meet the core eligibility criterion, namely displacement due to the 2022 Russian invasion of Ukraine. To ensure participants' eligibility, they will be asked a few questions during recruitment regarding their official status in the host country, year of arrival, and age.

As mentioned above, focus groups are typically composed of relatively homogenous participants in terms of knowledge of, or experience with, the research topic. Such homogeneity creates a benign environment in which participants are more likely to voice their views openly, resulting in richer discussion.⁹ In this research, participants are homogeneous in their background as Ukrainian war-refugees, but are heterogeneous across gender, age, and other variables.

To capture gender-based humour practices as well as multifaceted nature of the displacement, efforts will be made to ensure a gender-balanced sample. Age is another important variable for this research. Previous DELIAH's analysis of humorous practices has shown the age-related dynamic in which younger people engage with online humour more than older people.¹⁰ Beside socio-demographic variables of participants per se, the attention will be drawn to the heterogeneity of each case country. For example, Flanders and Wallonia are two culturally and linguistically distinct regions in Belgium. In case of Estonia, the northeast region (Ida-Viru county) and the capital city, Tallinn, represent a dense concentration of the Russophones, as opposed to, for instance, Tartu. Thus, taking this variable into account enables to understand a role of the country-specific aspects, such as inter-ethnic tensions, in relation to the adjustment through humour. The previous research on online humorous practices among Ukrainian refugees has shown differences in linguistic jokes in Flanders and Wallonia, as well as the presence of ethnic humour in Estonia.

In both countries, similar individual interviews and focus groups will ensure gender heterogeneity and proportionality, while also striving for representativeness in terms of participants' age, city of residence, and backgrounds to capture a wide range of voices and perspectives. Therefore, the number of participants from Belgium will be divided equally between Wallonia, Flanders and Brussels. The same applies to Estonia, with participants coming from its southern, north-eastern and western regions, as well as the capital, Tallinn. Four focus groups should be organised with four to six participants each per country. Each group is designed to capture regional diversity in humour practices among Ukrainian refugees, taking into account linguistic and socio-demographic differences.

The compositions of Focus Group 1 and Focus Group 2 are largely similar, differing primarily in terms of participants' places of residence. For the convenience and clear navigation between the focus groups, each of them will be allocated with a sub number (see Table 1). In Estonia, Focus Group 1.1 will be conducted in Ida-Viru County or Tallinn, both of which are predominantly Russophone areas, while Focus Group 2.1 will take place in Tartu or Pärnu, which are primarily Estonian-speaking environments. In Belgium, Focus Group 1.2 will be organized in Antwerp (Flanders), the Dutch-speaking region, while Focus Group 2.1 will take place in Liège (Wallonia) which is predominantly French-speaking. Both focus groups are designed to reflect the perspectives and experiences of the largest age cohort among Ukrainian

⁹ Julius Sim, "Collecting and Analysing Qualitative Data: Issues Raised by the Focus Group," *Journal of Advanced Nursing* 28, no. 2 (1998): 348, <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2648.1998.00692.x>.

¹⁰ Marcos Engelken-Jorge and Carmelo Moreno, *Meta-Analysis of Contemporary Humour Practices and Democratic Attitudes*, Zenodo, August 29, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.16994514>.

refugees granted temporary protection.¹¹ For the purposes of this framework, the lower boundary of this age range will be extended to 27 years and 64 years, and the group will be categorized as “middle-aged.” To ensure gender balance and inclusivity, participants will include men and women, as well as, where possible, individuals identifying as non-binary or other gender identities.

This age group largely comprises working-age adults, many of whom have migrated with children or other family members. At this stage of life, individuals typically bear significant familial and economic responsibilities and face a range of displacement-related challenges, including employment, housing, childcare, legal documentation, and socio-cultural adaptation.

Focus Group 3 will consist of younger participants (age 18-26), including men and women, as well as, where possible, individuals identifying as non-binary or other gender identities, all of whom hold refugee status. Individuals in this age category are typically active users of social media and are more likely to engage with and be familiar with contemporary trends and forms of online Ukrainian humour. Moreover, they often display relatively high levels of social adjustment, including language acquisition and the development of peer networks within the host society. This focus group may be conducted in student-oriented cities, such as Tartu in Estonia (Focus Group 3.1) and Ghent in Belgium (Focus Group 3.2), or alternatively in the respective capital cities.

An additional Focus Group 4 comprising early-career researchers, PhD candidates, and academics aims at capturing perspectives of highly educated adults. Shaped by the higher levels of education and analytical training, representatives of this group might demonstrate greater reflexivity in describing their experiences as well as offering critical interpretation of social, cultural, and political contexts. The professional environment, networks, and social status of these individuals as intellectuals are likely to influence their humour practices in a distinctive way. Furthermore, as Ukrainian refugees, beside the common challenges of displacement, they may encounter specific obstacles related to the recognition of qualifications and adjustment to the host-country institutions.

The final Focus Group 5 will consist of senior Ukrainian refugees of aged 65 and above, who are either retired or eligible for a pension. Previous research indicates that older refugees are largely overlooked and underrepresented being, despite heightened vulnerability as a social group.¹² Individuals in this age category often face specific challenges related to health and access to social protection, while being increasingly depended on the governmental support. Moreover, they may experience forms of exclusion from humanitarian responses, which typically prioritize women and children.¹³ Including seniors into the methodological framework, allows to capture generational difference in humour practices which usually shaped by the barriers to the digital technologies, broader forms of social exclusion associated with this age category, and uncover their experience with host-country healthcare system. At the same time, senior refugees act as custodians of humour practices that are progressively diminishing due to the rapid digitalization. Therefore, it will allow for exploration of how old genres and forms acquire new meanings in the context of displacement.

¹¹ Eurostat. “Temporary Protection for Persons Fleeing Ukraine – Monthly Statistics.” 2026. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Temporary_protection_for_persons_fleeing_Ukraine_-_monthly_statistics&oldid=584697#Who_are_the_people_fleeing_Ukraine_and_receiving_temporary_protection.3F

¹² Hachem, Sarah, Souad Ali, Sarah Al-Omari, Maya Abi Chahine, Sasha Abdallah Fahme, and Abia Mehio Sibai. “Older People Tend to Be Invisible”: A Qualitative Study Exploring the Needs and Inclusion of Older Syrian Refugees in the Context of Compounding Crises in Host Country, Lebanon.” *Conflict and Health* 16, no. 1 (November 19, 2022): 61. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13031-022-00496-4>.

¹³ Karunakara, Unni, and Frances Stevenson. “Ending Neglect of Older People in the Response to Humanitarian Emergencies.” *PLoS Medicine* 9, no. 12 (December 18, 2012): e1001357. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1001357>.

A pragmatic approach will be adopted, allowing respondents to choose the language of participation (Ukrainian and/or Russian). Focus groups are planned to take place in person. However, alternative arrangements (e.g., online participation) may be considered in exceptional circumstances, for instance, in the case of Focus Group 5 due to their lower physical mobility. The language of communication will be agreed upon in advance.

Table 1: Composition of the Focus Groups

FOCUS GROUP 1			
FOCUS GROUP 1.1	Men and women, possibly also non-binary or gender-diverse people, aged 27-64, having migrated to Estonia after February 2022 due to the war and residing in Tartu (Southern Estonia) or Pärnu (Western Estonia) . The sample should ensure a certain balance between men and women, and possibly representatives of other genders.	FOCUS GROUP 1.2	Men and women, possibly also non-binary or 'other'-gender people, aged 27-64, having migrated to Belgium after February 2022 due to the war and residing in Antwerp (Flanders) . The sample should ensure a certain balance between men and women, and possibly representatives of other genders.
FOCUS GROUP 2			
FOCUS GROUP 2.1	Men and women, possibly also non-binary or gender-diverse people, aged 27-64, having migrated to Estonia after February 2022 due to the war and residing in Tallinn or Ida-Viru county (Eastern Estonia) . The sample should ensure a certain balance between men and women, and possibly representatives of other genders.	FOCUS GROUP 2.2	Men and women, possibly also non-binary or 'other'-gender people, aged 27-64, having migrated to Belgium after February 2022 due to the war and residing in Liège (Wallonia, Belgium) . The sample should ensure a certain balance between men and women, and possibly representatives of other genders.
FOCUS GROUP 3			
FOCUS GROUP 3.1	Young women and men Mix (young people), possibly also non-binary or gender-diverse people, having migrated to Estonia after February 2022 due to the war and residing in a student-oriented city such as Tartu or the capital Tallinn .	FOCUS GROUP 3.2	Young women and men Mix (young people), possibly also non-binary or 'other'-gender people, having migrated to Belgium after February 2022 due to the war and residing in a student-oriented city such as Ghent or Leuven , or the capital Brussels .
FOCUS GROUP 4			
FOCUS GROUP 4.1	Young women and men	FOCUS GROUP 4.2	Young women and men

	Mix (young people), possibly also non-binary or gender-diverse people, having migrated to Estonia after February 2022 due to the war. Participants must be a PhD candidates, young researchers, or academics.		Mix (young people), possibly also non-binary or 'other'-gender people, having migrated to Belgium after February 2022 due to the war. Participants must be a PhD candidates, young researchers, or academics.
FOCUS GROUP 5			
FOCUS GROUP 5.1	Senior women and men 65+ who migrated to Estonia February 2022 due to the war.	FOCUS GROUP 5.2	Senior women and men 65+ who migrated to Belgium after February 2022 due to the war.

Table 2: Operationalisation of Relevant Variables

Variable	Indicators
Men, women, non-binary, other	People who self-describe as 'men', 'women', 'non-binary', 'other'.
Young people	People aged 18–26.
Middle-aged	People aged 27–64.
Senior people	People aged 65+

All data-collection activities will follow a standardized protocol to ensure ethical compliance, participant comfort, and methodological consistency. Each session—whether a focus group or an individual interview—will begin with introductory questions designed to help participants and the moderator become acquainted and to create a relaxed atmosphere, emphasizing that there are no right or wrong answers. Participants may also be invited to share their initial thoughts and feelings related to the topic in order to launch the conversation or reflect on their experience in the host country.

To guarantee confidentiality, participants will be asked to choose a pseudonym, which will be used throughout the discussion and in all subsequent documentation. Although informed consent forms will be shared digitally in advance, two printed copies will be provided on site. At the start of each session, the moderator will reiterate the content of the informed consent form, clarify the purpose of the research, outline participants' rights, explain the voluntary nature of their involvement, and describe the format of the interview or focus group. One signed copy of the consent form will remain with the participant. It is also important to reassure participants that there are no wrong answers and that their perspectives are valued.

All sessions will be audio-recorded using a digital device to ensure accurate documentation of the discussion. Recordings will be accessible only to members of the research team directly involved in the project and will not be shared externally. The interviews and focus groups will be digitally recorded and transcribed either manually or using transcription software. The gathered material will be stored on the university's cloud storage and backed up on the researcher's personal password-protected hard drive. The data will be kept in these repositories for the duration of the DELIAH project and for four years thereafter. Upon expiration of this period (March 2033), it will be permanently deleted. Access to the collected material will not be granted to anyone who is not involved in the current research project.

5 SCRIPT FOR FOCUS GROUPS

The focus group script is also divided into three sections: an introduction, a section in which participants are asked key questions related to the research and shown different examples of humour to develop a discussion, and a wrapping-up section in which participants are asked to provide any final suggestions and comments about the topic. Each focus group is expected to last between 60 and 120 minutes in total.

5.1 Section 1: Introduction

The objective of the research is to understand the adjustment of Ukrainian refugees in the host societies and the role humour plays in this process. In particular, how humour reveals the complexity of their experience and the broader socio-political attitudes towards them, under the assumption that humour communicates serious meanings. Furthermore, it includes the functions of humour among Ukrainian displaced people and whether their humour is specific to them or complies with global, Ukrainian, or local trends, enabling to identify the thematic repertoire that emerges in displacement in conjunction with the forms and genres of humorous practices. This will also allow us to explore gender differences.

Participants can be asked to share their initial thoughts and feelings related to the topic in order to launch the discussion or reflect on their experience in the host country.

Tentative questions that can be addressed to the participants in this section. They also can serve as transitional questions to move to the next section:

- *In everyday life, people use humour for different situations. In your opinion, what is the relationship between humour and adjustment in your lives? What role does it play in your experience as displaced people?*
- *Could you please describe what kind of humour you engage with or enjoy in everyday life? How do you share it? With whom? Is it more political or social? How do you think your preferences changed with migration?*

5.2 Section 2: Discussion

In this section, key questions are being asked. Humorous stimuli are used solely to encourage the discussion and to understand participants' views on various issues shared online about and by displaced Ukrainians (Annex 1). The main purpose of this section is to explore in depth their personal experiences of adjustment and engagement with vernacular humour practices in the case countries.

The section will require most of the time and will last approximately 60 minutes.

Key questions that should be addressed to the participants on this stage of the focus group. The order is rather arbitrary; however, the sequence should be appropriate for the flow of the discussion.

- *How would you describe the role humour plays when people talk about difficult experiences or challenges?*
 - **Follow-up questions:** *Can you think of any jokes or funny stories that people share about life as displaced people? Where do you usually see or hear this humour? (friends, social media, family)*

- *In your opinion, are Ukrainians a humorous people? What makes you say so? How about Estonians/Belgians?*
- *Humour about migration can be characterised as dark, ironic, or sarcastic. Do you know any dark jokes? Do you like dark humour overall? What do you think, what are the topics you cannot joke about among Ukrainians? Are there any topics you personally would never find funny? What if it is about Russians or refugees from the Middle East?*
 - *Do you joke about other refugees (in Belgium)/ Russians (in Estonia)?*
- *Are there any jokes, phrases, or memes that only Ukrainians here would really understand? Do your friends or family members who stayed in Ukraine understand these jokes too? Could you share an example?*
- *Was there ever a time in your life when humour felt impossible or inappropriate? Could you tell me about that and why it felt that way?*

5.3 Section 3: Wrap up

The questions in this section can be asked situationally, depending on the level of participants' engagement during the interview. At this stage, the group is simply thanked for their time and contribution to the study and invited to share any final thoughts they may have. The final stage involves the distribution of the participant incentive.

Tentative questions that can be addressed to the participants in this section:

- *Is there a particular phrase, meme, joke, or saying that you find yourself repeating often because it really fits your situation here?*
 - *Do you joke more in person or through messages? Are there social media platforms where you share funny content with close friends or family?*

6 SCRIPT FOR THE INDIVIDUAL INTERVIEWS

The script for individual interviews is organized into three sections to guide the flow of the conversation. This structure helps to establish a comfortable atmosphere for the participant with a gradual progression from general and less sensitive topics to more topic-specific questions. Each interview is expected to last between 60 to 120 minutes. Prior to the individual interview, each participant will be asked to share their favourite meme or joke. The shared material will be discussed during the interview.

6.1 Section 1: Introduction

This section is also known as the icebreaker, where the interviewer establishes a comfortable setting for the participants by introducing themselves and thanking the interlocutors for their time.

Tentative questions that can be addressed to the participants in this section. They also can serve as transitional questions to move to the next section:

- *Could you share with me the story of your journey from Ukraine to Belgium/Estonia?*
- *Were there any unexpected or funny moments during your trip or when you first arrived?*

- *How are you finding life here? What has the adjustment been like for you? What kinds of difficulties or challenges do you face in your daily life here?*
- *How often do you find yourself joking or laughing these days (also compared to the time in Ukraine)? Who do you usually share these moments with?*
- *Can you think of a recent story, phrase, or moment that made you laugh? Do funny things happen often for you here?*
- *Who do you laugh with and how do you share humor? On what topics?*
- *How do you usually talk about your life here with friends? Are there moments when you laugh or joke about your experiences?*

6.2 Section 2: Humour and adjustment specific questions

In this section, the participants will be asked the key questions to gather insights into the research topic. The section will require most of the time and will last approximately 60 minutes.

Tentative questions that can be addressed to the participants in this section:

- *How would you describe the role of humor in your life right now?*
- *Have you had any funny or absurd experiences dealing with social services or with any kind of services?*
- *Do you have any funny comparisons of how things work here and in Ukraine?*
- *Do you know any dark jokes? Do you like dark humour overall? What do you think, what are the topics you cannot joke about among Ukrainians? Are there any topics you personally would never find funny? What if it is about Russians?*
- *Are there moments when people joke about the war? Who do you feel comfortable sharing these jokes with? How do you feel when non-Ukrainians make jokes about it?*
 - *Was there ever a time in your life when humor felt impossible or inappropriate? Could you tell me about that and why it felt that way?*
- *Humour about migration can be characterised as dark, ironic, or sarcastic. Do you know any dark jokes? Do you like dark humour overall? What do you think, what are the topics you cannot joke about among Ukrainians? Are there any topics you personally would never find funny? What if it is about Russians or refugees from the Middle East?*
 - *Do you joke about other refugees (in Belgium)/ Russians (in Estonia)?*
- *Are there any jokes, phrases, or memes that only Ukrainians here would really understand?*
 - *Do your friends or family members who stayed in Ukraine understand these jokes too? Could you share an example?*
- *In your opinion, are Ukrainians a humorous people? What makes you say so? How about Estonians/Belgians?*
- *Do you share humor with local people here? Are there things you find funny about each other? Do you have a special humorous name/nickname for those people? Have you heard any ethnic jokes about locals?*
 - *Do you joke more in person or through messages? Are there social media platforms where you share funny content with close friends or family?*

6.3 Section 3: Wrap-up

The questions in this section can be asked situationally, depending on how active and enthusiastic the participant was throughout the interview. At this stage, the interviewee is simply thanked for their time and contribution to the study and invited to share any final thoughts they may have. The final stage involves the distribution of the participant incentive.

Tentative questions that can be addressed to the participants in this section:

- *The question about language acquisition is probably the most common among Ukrainian displaced people. How is your language learning going (Dutch/French/Estonian)? Could you share a story?*
- *Is there a particular phrase, meme, joke, or saying that you find yourself repeating often because it really fits your situation here*

ANNEX 1

Humorous stimuli for the Focus Group Discussions

This annex contains a pre-selection of the stimuli for the focus groups. Some of the stimuli were sourced from the Saving Ukrainian Cultural Heritage Online (SUCHO) initiative, which uses crowdsourcing to collect Ukrainian war memes. Previous research on the online humour of Ukrainian refugees also informed the selection. The videos presented here are part of the sample used in that earlier study.

Stimulus 1

“Jealous Cat” or “Cat Looking at Man Holding Dog” meme embodies the sentiment among some refugees about unequal border regime by the Western countries, including the EU.

Figure 1. Translation into Ukrainian: Світ, українські біженці (зверху ліворуч); біженці з Близького сходу (наступні три картинки)

Justification: This image macros is well-known meme. Ukrainians are most likely familiar with it. This meme can help to open the discussion on the attitudes of the border regime in the EU and reflection of Ukrainians on their position among other refugees.

Stimulus 2

Trump-Zelenskyy Oval Office meeting on August 25 amidst two big scandals both in Ukraine and the US – the operation Midas (Mindich tapes) and Witkoff tapes. Mindich is a Ukrainian oligarch and close friend of the president Zelenskyy. Witkoff is the US special envoy to Russia.

Figure 2. Zelenskyy and Trump shaking hands, finding a compromise. Translation: - I know about Mindich tapes,- Trump. -I know about Witkoff tapes,- Zelenskyy

Justification: This example encompasses three various political events and allows to open discussion on how Ukrainian refugees engage with the global and Ukrainian humorous trends. Firstly, the biggest corruption scandal in Ukraine. Secondly, the scandal around the US special envoy on how to approach Trump. Third, the meltdown in the US-Ukraine relationship after the quarrel in the Oval Office earlier that year.

Stimulus 3

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1c9HDPLqrvKAz3fw3l4gM-O3Uue8H_W2E/view?usp=share_link

TikTok trend popular among Ukrainians abroad.

Translation: I dream that the war in Ukraine is over and Estonians have come to us to work. I make them learn Ukrainian and tell them, 'mine Eesti'. Their salary is 2500 uah.

Justification: This TikTok video help to introduce the discussion about Ukrainians in their host societies.

Stimulus 4 (Estonia)

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AflDINXLfeM5W1pHCssH8naHfqKvw8X/view?usp=share_link

TikTok trend popular among Ukrainians in Estonia.

Justification : This example reflects the attitudes of local population towards Ukrainian displaced people (in this case Russophones in Estonia). This video will be used to open the discussion on ethnic friction in the host countries.

Stimulus 5

Select All Squares is a series of images that mock Google’s CAPTCHA (Completely Automated Public Turing test to tell Computers and Humans Apart), which instruct users to “select all squares” that match a specified label to prove that a user is not a robot. Here the meme is about selecting a “good Russian.”

Figure 3. Select all images with good Russians

t.me/smehinki_net	 "Liberal" russian (starts conversation with "but what about...")	
Xenophobic	✓	✓
Imperialistic	✓	✓
Fascist	✓	✓
Approves a Genocide of Ukrainians	✓	✓ wants it to be more effective
Pro-Putin	✓	✗
Crimea is Russia	✓	✓

Figure 4. Additional meme. The meme compares an ordinary Russian with a "liberal" Russian (a member of the Russian opposition), suggesting that the only difference between them is that the latter is not pro-Putin.

Translation into Ukrainian: Звичайний росіянин (дуже звичайний (ліворуч)); «ліберальний» росіянин (починає розмову зі слів: «але що на рахунок...»)(праворуч)). Стовпці (зверху вниз): ксенофоб, імперіаліст, фашист, згоден з геноцидом українців (праворуч: хоче щоб це було більш ефективніше), про-Путініст, Крим-Росія.

Justification: This meme continues the theme of ethnic frictions. Russophobia and attitudes toward the Russian opposition whom Ukrainians perceive rather sceptical, suspecting them in insincerity and lingering imperialist thinking, are central targets of humour in Ukraine.

Stimulus 6

The post from Threads refers to popular reaction GIFs featuring Eduardo Sterblitch (on the left), attempting to suppress laughter, and Shaquille O'Neal smiling knowingly.

Figure 5. Translation: "The whole world: 'This is not a topic for jokes.' Ukrainians:"

Justification: This stimulus reflects the nature of contemporary Ukrainian humour and allows for the commencement of a discussion about what is considered laughable and what is not.

Stimulus 7

The continuing heavy toll on the Ukrainian Armed Forces, coupled with persistent personnel shortages and inequalities on the battlefield, has forced Ukraine to accelerate its mobilization efforts. In response, the government introduced legislation to penalize draft evasion, aiming to ensure that all eligible citizens contribute to the defence effort. Territorial Recruitment Offices (TCC) have been tasked with conscripting new soldiers, often under challenging conditions amid widespread resistance, public reluctance, and tense confrontations with draft dodgers.

Коли зранку йдеш на роботу.

Figure 6. When you go to work in the morning. TCC (helicopter) and a potential conscript (Rambo)

Justification: This example reflects the attitude of Ukrainian refugees towards draft evaders.

Stimulus 8

Both sides have suffered heavy losses in the Russo-Ukrainian war. According to available statistics, Russians lost over a million military personnel.¹ For Ukrainians, ridiculing Russian soldiers, weather dead or alive, has become a common practice. In contrast, joking about Ukrainian soldiers has remained largely taboo.

¹ Armed Forces of Ukraine. "Estimated enemy losses," n.d. <https://www.zsu.gov.ua>.

Figure 7. Translation: the key is not a prize, but participation.

Justification: This example reflects on the question whether there are a moral or social boundaries among Ukrainian refugees in joking about death, especially when it is about Russians.

Stimulus 9

Before becoming President, Volodymyr Zelenskyy was a successful comedian and actor, best known for his work with the comedy group and television production company “Kvartal 95,” which enjoyed widespread popularity in Ukraine. After winning the presidential election, he stepped away from entertainment to focus fully on politics. However, various clips from the show continue to circulate online, often taking on new meanings in different contexts. In one notable example, Zelenskyy and a colleague from “Kvartal 95” performed a provocative comedic sketch in which they used their genitals to play various pieces of classical music.

ЦЕ ЗЕЛЕНСЬКИЙ ГРАЄ ПІСНЮ "ДО ОСТАНЬОГО УКРАЇНЦЯ"

Figure 8. Translation: Zelenskyy plays a song "Until the last Ukrainian."

Justification: This example allows to explore public attitude toward Ukrainian President Volodymyr Zelenskyy among Ukrainian displaced and the controversies emerged during his presidential term.

Stimulus 10

Including language acquisition stimuli was informed by the previous research on Ukrainian displaced people's online humour. This theme was the largest what allows to think that language learning is the most important aspect for Ukrainian forced migrants.

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1bbMeyllwzkiLoZAYfeRCWfidNRUVFs91/view?usp=sharing>

Translation: We are not going to stay here in any way. Why do you bother?

Justification: This example opens the discussion on Ukrainians' intentions to return back and how it influences their adjustment in the host society.

Stimulus 11

https://drive.google.com/file/d/195XgbE7oe-ZHF1PVp1Ad_jUZHwVLGTvc/view?usp=sharing

Translation: When I'm asked why I haven't learnt Dutch yet. I have a weak short-term memory.

Justification : This stimulus continues the exploration of cultural and linguistic adjustment.